

DECOLONIZING DIGITAL PRESERVATION AND ACCESS: CASE STUDIES FROM A CANADIAN UNIVERSITY ARCHIVES AND LIBRARY

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Submission Type – Poster.

Keywords – Community, Collaboration, Access, Data sovereignty

Conference Topics – Tūhono - Connect

As Canada concludes the first decade of a post-Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) society, professionals in archives and libraries have sought to respond in constructive ways by addressing the TRC's 94 Calls to Action and particularly to those calls related to heritage work. Calls 67 and 70, for example, ask the heritage community to review policies in consultation with Indigenous partners and align values with the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP).

The Truth and Reconciliation of Canada (TRC) issued its final report in 2015. The TRC was established in 2008 with the mandate to document and expose the vast harms of Canada's Indian Residential School system, which was established in the 19th century with the last school closing in 1997. The TRC heard and documented school survivor and witness statements across the country and collected copies of church and government records which are housed at the National Centre for Truth and Reconciliation in Winnipeg, Manitoba. The TRC published a multi-volume report and issued 94 Calls to Action directed to government and many sectors

of society; call #70 to the archival community is one of 15 of the 94 that some have judged completed to date.

How do these calls to action affect the work of librarians and archivists working in the digital preservation sphere?

Drawing upon the ongoing work of two professionals who are increasingly engaged in these issues at a Canadian university, the University of Victoria (UVic), this poster outlines four institutionally-specific digital preservation and access case studies that address the iPRES theme of Tūhono (Connect). To be clear, these professionals are non-Indigenous scholars. Given the location and content of our collections, Indigenous-settler relations are an inevitable aspect of our work and we seek to engage with this in meaningful and thoughtful ways. Two case studies centre upon archival collections and two involve library patron research support.

Our case studies will examine how the Canadian societal context of working towards Truth and Reconciliation frames our work at our university. We will cover how Indigenous Language Revitalization students and researchers must navigate oppressive cultural barriers in the institution and the colonial heritage system, such as existing preservation and library metadata that complicate access; how we are

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learning to practice cultural safety and humility by establishing a culturally safe environment for Indigenous students we work with, and at the same time teaching non-Indigenous students cultural humility. We will describe how the lessons of the First Nations' Information Governance Council's "Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession" principles inform our archival work in choosing preservation systems and processes, and shifting access control to the Indigenous people whose information it is. This involves everything from choosing transfer package contents (we use Archivematica) to establishing an access agreement with a large First Nation.

We will discuss our experiences mediating respectful preservation and access in our journeys as we have sought to develop Indigenous cultural acumen while also navigating institutional barriers to digital preservation and respecting data sovereignty. Through viewing this poster, attendees will learn how an archivist and a librarian regularly seek to address issues of digital preservation and patron access to collections that focus on Indigenous topics in respectful ways.

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